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BIOCHEMICAL INDICATORS OF ORAL FLUID OF CHILDREN WITH CONCOMITANT THYROPATHOLOGY

Abstract:

A clinical and paraclinical studies of children 12 years with chronic catarrhal gingivitis and diffuse toxic goiter I-II degree. Activation of collagen degradation and reduce the intensity of collagen formation and reduce the concentration of glycoproteins of saliva under these conditions.

Key word: children, gingivitis, diffuse toxic goiter, collagen, glycoproteins.

Today, thyroid diseases are one of the most common non-infectious human diseases. The increasing interest in the problem of thyroid pathology is caused by its growing prevalence and negative impact on the intellectual, general educational and professional potential of the nation [7]. Equally important is the influence of thyroid status on the normal physical growth and development of the child, as well as the course of a number of concomitant diseases. The main dental diseases are caries and periodontopathies, which affect the vast majority of the population from childhood, and often develop against the background of thyroid pathology. This leads to certain clinical features of the course of dental pathology, which requires a full diagnosis and adequate correction. A number of clinical observations of patients who have combined dental and thyroid pathologies are known from the literature [2,4,5]. Clinical features of the course of caries, its complications, gingivitis and characteristic signs of the formation of the dentofacial apparatus in children under such conditions have been established [1,3]. However, the issues of early and informative diagnosis of pathogenetic changes in hard and soft tissues of the oral cavity in children with altered thyroid status remain problematic, making it possible to correctly assess the severity of the lesion and select etiopathogenetic treatment. No less important, in our opinion, in pediatric dentistry is the direction of non-invasive diagnostic procedures, excluding the possibility of infection and the action of a stress factor. Oral fluid is the optimal biomaterial because it is a fairly informative source of research. In addition, this method of research is attractive due to the simplicity of collecting material and the possibility of repeated sampling.

Purpose our work was define indicators exchange collagen and glycoproteins oral fluids in children with chronic hepatitis and concomitant pathology thyroid glands

For this purpose, we conducted a clinical dental examination of 90 children with diffuse non-toxic goiter (DNG) of I-II severity, as well as 30 somatically healthy children aged 12 years. The contingent of children with thyropathies was recruited from patients of the endocrinology department of the Regional Chil-

dren's Hospital and the city children's clinic (Chernivtsi). The control group of children was selected from students of secondary schools in the city. All children are divided into 4 observation groups: Group I – dentally and somatically healthy children (30 people); Group II - dentally healthy children with DD (30 people); Group III – children with D ND and mild CHG (30 people); Group IV – children with D ND and CHCH of moderate and severe severity (30 people). Diagnosis of endocrine pathology was carried out in accordance with the Protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of endocrinological diseases in children of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine. The condition of periodontal tissues was assessed according to its symptoms of damage in sextants according to WHO recommendations without taking into account periodontal pockets, the severity of gingivitis was determined by the papillary-marginal-alveolar index of the PMA (C. Parma, 1960). The diagnosis was based on the classification of periodontal diseases by N.F. Danilevsky (1994). Oral hygiene status was determined using the simplified oral hygiene index OIH-S (J.C. Green, J.R. Vermillion, 1964).

For the paraclinical study, oral fluid was used, which was collected in the morning on an empty stomach after rinsing the mouth twice with distilled water by spitting into a disposable tube in an amount of 5 ml. Total protein levels were determined using the Lowry O method, concentration of glycoproteins according to the method of Romanenko E.G. [8]. The intensity of collagen metabolism processes was assessed by the content of free and bound hydroxyproline by reaction with n-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde [6].

Statistical processing of the data was carried out using the method of variation statistics using the Student's test using the STATISTICA 6 computer program.

Our research has shown the following results. Prevalence diseases of periodontal tissues in somatic patients healthy children amounted to 63.3 %, and was approximately 12 % lower than in those examined with DLD. In structure periodontal tissue diseases prevails chronic catarrhal gingivitis, prevalence whom reaches indicators 92-94 %. The disease was predominantly

chronic, exacerbation process was noted in 10.5 % of those examined.

For determining degrees gravity inflammatory the process in the gums was counted papillary - marginal - alveolar index (PMA). Determined that RMA index with increasing degrees the severity of CHCG increased to 20.3 % and 62.8 %. Summing up results RMA index should say that children with diffuse nontoxic goiter predominated gingivitis average degrees gravity.

Definition index bleeding in children showed the presence differences between indicators in all groups observations with magnification degrees gravity pathology ($p < 0.05$). However, unlike the previous index, change indicators according to degrees gravity various: most swift height symptom bleeding noted between groups I and II (by 68.57 %). This leads to the conclusion that in children with the studied pathology HCG progression is associated, first of all, with a violation structures and functions circulatory vessels

and surrounding tissues, which it has place for long-term thyroid dysfunction.

According to carried out according to WHO recommendations analysis condition of periodontal tissues by quantity affected sextants, results whom are given in table. 1. Definition quantities affected (according to the Schiller-Pisarev test) and healthy several sextants showed opposite results worsened with increasing degrees gravity pathology. Received data emphasized again bias visual examinations and less accurate assessment degrees severity compared to the score interpretation Therefore, upon inspection prevalence and severity process in children Seems less than there really is case.

Estimation based on data criteria were carried out separately in girls and boys. Indicators periodontal tissue damage were girls are higher indicates the onset of puberty, which often accompanied by juvenile gingivitis.

Table 1

Degree lesions of periodontal tissue in sextants, M ± m

Group	Bleeding ness	Dental stone	Schiller-Pisarev test	Healthy gum
Control	0	0	0	6.0 ± 0.00
Group II	1.09 ± 0.01	0	2.34 ± 0.05	3.66 ± 0.20
Group III	2.7 ± 0.23*	0.06 ± 0.002*	3.8 ± 0.27*	2.2 ± 0.18*
Group IV	3.5 ± 0.24*	0.1 ± 0.02*	4.3 ± 0.41*	1.7 ± 0.12*

Note: * - reliable difference indicators with the control group , $p < 0.05$.

Received results indicate reliable increasing everyone periodontal indexes and samples that indicates deterioration condition of periodontal tissues in children who have accompanying pathology thyroid glands How known to be periodontopathy have multifactorial nature with predominance inflammatory or dystrophic processes. To establish etiopathogenetic mechanism emergence We analyzed the pathologies of periodontal tissues in conditions of neurological diseases possible periodontopathogenic risk factors .

Hygiene oral cavities according to index ONI-S is in unsatisfactory level in all groups surveillance and control, can become a trigger mechanism formation diffuse inflammatory process in the gums . In particular , average values simplified index were 1.83 ± 0.12 in children of group II, 1.69 ± 0.4 in group III, 1.93 ± 0.14 in group IV, and did not have reliable differences between itself and indicator control group (1.74 ± 0.16).

Local provoking factors of inflammatory process are carious lesions, dentofacial anomalies, etc. As

shown by our studies with increasing degrees severity of chronic hepatitis in children increases quantity carious, including untreated carious cavities What concerns dentofacial anomalies and deformations, then their frequency of detection Also had there was a tendency to increase with thyroid pathology, but there was no such swift like caries.

The results of the biochemical study are presented in Table 2. The protein content in the oral fluid of dentally healthy children with underlying endocrinological pathology was higher than in the control group, although there was no significant difference between these indicators. But the protein level increased significantly with combined dental and somatic pathologies. Obviously, an increase in the level of protein in the oral fluid is a compensatory phenomenon and indicates strain in the functioning of the salivary glands, as well as increased transudation of proteins during the inflammatory process in the gums.

Table 2

Indicators oral liquids children with diffuse non-toxic goiter

Index	Group I (M± m)	Group II (M± m)	III group (M± m)	IV group (M ± m)
General protein, mg/ml	2.13 ± 0.01	2.75 ± 0.14	3.43 ± 0.14*	3.98 ± 0.17*
Free hydroxyproline, mcg /ml	0.21 ± 0.01	0.19 ± 0.01	0.25 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.03*
Hydroxyproline bound to protein, µg / ml	0.64 ± 0.05	0.59 ± 0.03	0.50 ± 0.03*	0.45 ± 0.02*
Glycoproteins, mg/ml	0.15 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01*	0.04 ± 0.01*	0.03 ± 0.01*

Note: * - reliable difference indicators with the control group , $p < 0.05$.

At the same time, the content of protein-carbohydrate complexes of saliva - glycoproteins decreased in all observation groups. In particular, it doubled in children of group II and 3-4 times in those examined in groups III-IV. A decrease in the level of glycoproteins against the background of an increase in protein content may indicate their possible breakdown and impaired maturation under these conditions. This idea is confirmed by the registered increase in the concentration of individual hydrocarbon components such as fucose and sialic acids against the background of a decrease in the level of hexosamines.

The analysis of the main structural component of periodontal bone tissue - collagen - turned out to be interesting. In children with CCH, activation of collagen degradation processes was observed, which was manifested by an increase in the level of free hydroxyproline. At the same time, in all children with concomitant thyroid pathology, the intensity of the process of collagen synthesis decreased, evidence of which is a decrease in the level of hydroxyproline associated with protein.

The results of the study of the connective tissue components of the dentoalveolar segment indicate the need to correct these disorders, which may lead to an improvement in the quality of medical care for such children.

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